

COMMUNITY EMPOWERMENT STRATEGY IN AGROTOURISM VILLAGE DEVELOPMENT IN KUNINGAN REGENCY

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Abstract

Agrotourism is one form of rural tourism that offers agricultural activities as a tourist attraction and involves local residents in planning and managing agrotourism areas. One of the principles of sustainable agrotourism development is community participation in planning. The development of agrotourism-based local potential has a positive impact on farmers, rural communities, and village governments. However, on the other hand, because the development of this potential relies on natural resources, its development is also very dependent on nature. In addition, the limited budget and the role of village governments to create excellent programs in supporting the development of agrotourism-based local potential. Kuningan Regency has agrotourism potential with superior objects, processed products made from plants and fruits, cultural uniqueness and beautiful panorama. Community Empowerment Strategy in Agrotourism Development in Kuningan Regency can be carried out through various trainings, which are more initiated by tourism actors. While the government provides facilities in the form of providing places. One of the trainings that can be done is training to become a professional guide, training on homestay arrangement, and training on entrepreneurial spirit.

Keywords: Community Empowerment, Agrotourism, Kuningan Regency.

INTRODUCTION

Based on Law No. 23 of 2014 concerning Local Government Chapter II article 2, it is stated that districts/cities are divided into sub-districts and sub-districts are divided into kelurahan and/or villages. In addition, the village has its own umbrella that specifically regulates villages, which is marked by the birth of Village Law No. 6 of 2014 concerning villages. In addition to the Village Law, the Ministry of Villages, PDT and Transmigration has also been established, which can provide new enthusiasm in supporting villages to be more independent and innovative. Based on Law No. 6 of 2014 concerning Villages, that: "Villages are villages and customary villages or referred to by other names, hereinafter referred to as Villages, are legal community units that have territorial boundaries that are authorized to regulate and manage government affairs, the interests of local communities based on community initiatives, rights of origin, and/or traditional rights that are recognized and respected in the government system of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia".

Based on the definition above, it shows that villages can exercise their own autonomy, namely running their government based on the rights of origin and customs, or what can be called original autonomy. In addition to regulations on village autonomy, the village law also explains village authority, one of which is the authority in the field of village development. The authority of village development is contained in Law No. 6 of 2014 Chapter IV article 18 that: "Authority

in the field of village governance, implementation of village development, village community development, and empowerment of village communities based on community initiatives, rights of origin, and village customs".

It is further explained that the authority of the village includes: First, authority based on the right of origin. According to Didik Sukrino (2010), the authority of the origin of the village includes the management of village assets, such as natural resource management. With this authority, the village can carry out village development in accordance with existing potential. Second, village-scale local authority. Third, the authority assigned by the Government, Provincial Regional Government, or Regency/City Regional Government. Fourth, other authorities assigned by the Government, Provincial Regional Government, or Regency/City Regional Government in accordance with the provisions of laws and regulations.

In accordance with Law No. 6 of 2014 concerning Villages, article 78 point (1) explains that the local economic potential of the village is a condition for village development aimed at improving the welfare of rural communities and the quality of human life. Village development in accordance with the potential and local resources owned can be used as an icon for the village. Therefore, the development of superior potential owned by one village can be different from other villages. This is because each village has a distinctive diversity, both in terms of economy, social, culture and geography. Based on Law No. 6 of 2014 concerning Villages Chapter I Article I, that "Village Development is an effort to improve the quality of life and life for the maximum welfare of the village community." The importance of efforts to support village development is followed up by the issuance of Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia Number 114 of 2015 concerning Village Development Guidelines. Based on the Ministerial Regulation that village development is carried out by the Village Government which is supported by the participation of the village community with the spirit of mutual cooperation.

Agrotourism is one form of rural tourism that offers agricultural activities as a tourist attraction and involves local residents in planning and managing agrotourism areas. According to Jolly and Reynolds (2005), agrotourism is a business carried out by farmers who work in the agricultural sector for the pleasure and education of visitors. Agrotourism is a business carried out by farmers who work in the agricultural sector for the pleasure and education of visitors. Agrotourism presents a potential source of income and increases community profits. Visitors to agrotourism areas can connect directly with farmers and support the improvement of agricultural products indirectly.

One of the principles of sustainable agrotourism development is community participation in planning. Local communities, especially indigenous people who live in tourist areas, become one of the key players in tourism, because they are the ones who will provide most of the attractions while determining the quality of tourism products (Damanik and Weber, 2006). The participation of this community is an important thing in an effort to maintain the integrity of nature and as an alternative in responding to the demands and urgency of sustainable tourism development.

The development of agrotourism-based local potential has a positive impact on farmers, rural communities, and village governments. However, on the other hand, because the development of this potential relies on natural resources, its development is also very dependent on nature. In addition, the limited budget and the role of village governments to create excellent programs in supporting the development of agrotourism-based local potential.

The development of Cibulan Village in Cidahu District in developing agrotourism potential is a shared responsibility between the government and the community. With the potential possessed by Cibulan Village in Cidahu District in the agrotourism sector, it will be very helpful in improving the economy of the village community. Through the agrotourism sector, the Village Government strives to achieve this goal by involving the community to jointly take village development initiatives, because in addition to being a local or regional potential, the role and awareness of the community in village development is encouraged and grown so that the results can be enjoyed by all levels of society.

Based on the background of the research and these problems, the research team is interested in conducting research entitled "Community Empowerment Strategy in the Development of Agrotourism Village in Kuningan Regency".

DISCUSSION

Community-Based Agrotourism Concept

Agrotourism is one form of tourism that relies on the agricultural sector or where tourists can learn about life in an agricultural area (Akpinar, 2003). Understanding agrotourism in the Joint Decree of the Minister of Agriculture and the Minister of Tourism, Post and Telecommunications Number: 204/KPTS/30HK/050/4/1989 and KM Number. 47/PW. DOW / MPPT / 89 concerning Coordination of Agro Tourism Development, defined as a form of tourism activity that utilizes agro business as a tourism object with the aim of expanding knowledge, travel, recreation and business relations in agriculture.

According to Jolly and Reynolds (2005), agrotourism is a business carried out by farmers who work in the agricultural sector for the pleasure and education of visitors. Agrotourism presents a potential source of income and increases community profits. Visitors to agrotourism areas can connect directly with farmers and support the improvement of agricultural products indirectly. Furthermore, Lobo et al (1999) explained that agrotourism development will offer opportunities for local farmers to increase their source of income and improve the quality and welfare of life in line with the sustainability of these activities. In addition, through the development of agrotourism that highlights local culture in utilizing land, we can increase farmers' income while preserving land resources, as well as maintaining local culture and technology (indigenous knowledge) which are generally in accordance with natural environmental conditions (Utama, 2011).

The development of an agrotourism area can play a role in improving the welfare of local communities and poverty alleviation. It can be categorized as Local Economic Development. The local economic development strategy needs to involve rural communities directly in

planning, implementing, evaluating, and monitoring the development of their tourism villages (Yoeti, 2008). Through this approach, it is hoped that tourism development as an industry will no longer only belong to investors (Yoeti, 2008). Local communities, especially indigenous people who live in tourist areas, become one of the key players in tourism, because they are the ones who will provide most of the attractions while determining the quality of tourism products (Damanik and Weber, 2006).

Community-based agrotourism shows community members organizing themselves and operating the agrotourism business based on rules and the distribution of duties and authorities that they have mutually agreed upon. Resources, especially farmland, remain the property of individual farmers but each of them may hand over the management of their assets to a group or management party of their determination in exchange for proportional benefits. Their shared capital assets are used to build infrastructure and basic facilities which are the minimum requirements for the development of the agrotourism center (Budiarsa, 2011 in Saridarmini, 2011). Some key aspects in the development of community-based agrotourism are the community forming a committee for agrowista management, local ownership, homestays as accommodation facilities, local people guides, management and maintenance are the responsibility of the community, sustainability from a social and environmental side, the principle of environmental carrying capacity is considered, environmentally friendly technology, and ecotourism conservancies (Saridarmini, 2011).

One approach to developing community-based agrotourism is with tourism villages. The development of rural areas no longer only controls the agricultural sector purely, but develops towards presenting tourism activities in the agricultural sector. Departing from this, the Ministry of Culture and Tourism created a program called Inti Rakyat Tourism (PIR) or in other terms, namely community-based tourism. According to PIR, Tourism Village is a rural area that offers an overall atmosphere that reflects the authenticity of the countryside both from socio-economic, socio-cultural, customary, daily life, has a distinctive building architecture and village spatial structure, or unique and interesting economic activities and has the potential to develop various components of tourism, for example: attractions, accommodation, food-drinks, and other tourism needs.

Community Empowerment Strategy in Agrotourism Development

Agrotourism or agrotourism in Indonesia is a form of tourism activities that utilize agro businesses (agribusiness) as tourist objects (<http://eprints.undip.ac.id>). The development of agrotourism based on local potential can have a positive impact on community members, the government and also the private sector. Efforts to develop agrotourism broadly cover 5 aspects (<http://database.deptan.go.id>), including: First, human resources (HR). Human resources play an important role in the development of agrotourism. Not only the availability of tour guides but also the knowledge and skills of guides related to tourist products.

Second, promotion can be done through various means, such as leaflets, booklets, exhibitions, souvenirs, mass media (in the form of advertisements or audiovisual media), as well as the provision of information in public places (hotels, airports, restaurants, etc.). In addition,

promotions can also be done by collaborating with travel and hospitality agencies / agents. Third, natural resources and the environment. Agrotourism business is very dependent on nature, so its sustainability depends on how efforts to maintain the sustainability and beauty of natural resources and the environment.

Fourth, support for facilities and infrastructure. Accessibility to reach agrotourism locations is something that cannot be underestimated. The ease of accommodation and transportation greatly supports the development of agrotourism business. As well as ease in providing services to visitors / tourists is also an important aspect in the success of agrotourism development. Fifth, institutional. Agrotourism development needs the role of various stakeholders, be it from the government, community, or private parties. The government acts as a facilitator in supporting the development of agrotourism in the form of ease of regulation so that there is no mutually lethal business climate. For this reason, cooperation between agrotourism object entrepreneurs, as well as between agrotourism objects and supporting institutions (tourist trips, hospitality and others) is very important.

The concept of "empowerment" comes from the root word "power" which means "strength", and is a translation from English that is "empowerment". In this case, the concept of empowerment means giving power or strength to weak groups who do not yet have the power / strength to live independently, especially in meeting basic needs / basic needs of daily life, such as food, clothing / clothing, house / shelter, education, and health (Hamid, 2018).

Conceptually, community empowerment can be defined as a social action of the residents of a community who organize themselves in making collective planning and action, to solve social problems or meet social needs in accordance with their abilities and resources (Sumodiningrat, 2009). In another opinion, community empowerment is defined as a concept of economic development that encapsulates social values. This concept reflects a new paradigm of development, which is people centered, participatory, empowering, and sustainable (Alfitri, 2011). In general, community empowerment is aimed at vulnerable and weak community groups, so that after being empowered they have the strength or ability to meet their basic needs. These basic needs include clothing, food, and shelter. In addition to being able to meet basic needs, the community is also expected to be able to reach productive sources that can increase their income and obtain the goods / services needed with good quality. In this case, the community is expected to be able to participate in the development process and decision-making that affects them (Suharto, 2010).

The main purpose of community empowerment is to give strength to the community, especially weak groups who have helplessness. This helplessness can result from internal conditions (their own perception), as well as external conditions (oppressed by unjust social structures). The hope is that after being empowered, the community can be more prosperous, empowered or have the strength to meet the main needs of life, and in the end will create an independent society. The independence referred to here is not only seen from the economic aspect, but also socially, culturally, and the right to voice / opinion, even to the independence of the community in determining their political rights (Hamid, 2018).

Jimmu, (2008) states that community development is not only limited to theories about how to develop rural areas but has a meaning that is possible development at the community level. Community development should reflect community action and awareness of self-identity. Therefore, a commitment to community development must recognize the interconnectedness between individuals and the communities to which they belong. Society is a structural phenomenon and that structural nature of a group or society has an effect on the way people act, feel and think. But when we look at such structures, they are clearly unlike the physical qualities of the outside world. They depend on the regularity of social reproduction, a society that only has an effect on people to the extent that structures are produced and reproduced in what people do. Therefore the development of society has a logical epistemological and a basic one in the social obligations that individuals have towards society that develops their talents.

Adedokun, et al., (2010) showed that effective communication will lead to active participation of community members in community development. He also revealed that when community groups are involved in communication strategies, it helps them take ownership of community development initiatives rather than seeing themselves as development beneficiaries. Based on these findings, it is recommended that community leaders as well as community development agents should engage in clear communication so as to solicit the participation of community members in its development issues.

The concept of empowerment emphasizes that people acquire sufficient skills, knowledge, and power to influence their lives and the lives of others who concern them (Pearson et al, 1994 in Sukmaniar, 2007). Understanding of the concept of empowerment cannot be separated from the understanding of the empowerment cycle itself, because in essence empowerment is a continuous effort to place the community to be more proactive in determining the direction of progress in their own community. This means that empowerment programs cannot only be carried out in one cycle and stop at a certain stage, but must continue and the quality continues to improve from one stage to the next (Mubarak, 2010).

According to Wilson (1996) there are 7 stages in the community empowerment cycle. The first stage is the desire of the community itself to change for the better. In the second stage, the community is expected to be able to release obstacles or factors that are resistant to progress in themselves and their communities. In the third stage, people are expected to have received additional freedom and feel a responsibility in developing themselves and their communities. The fourth stage is an effort to develop broader roles and boundaries of responsibility, it is also related to interest and motivation to do the job better. In this fifth stage tangible results of empowerment begin to show, where a greater increase in sense of belonging results in better performance outcomes. In the sixth stage there has been a change in behavior and impression of him, where success in improving performance is able to increase psychological feelings above the previous position. In the seventh stage, people who have succeeded in empowering themselves, feel challenged for greater efforts to obtain better results. This empowerment cycle describes the process of individual and community efforts to follow the journey towards higher individual and job achievement and satisfaction.

If examined from a series of literature on the concepts of Community Empowerment, the concept of empowerment is a process that is sought to make changes. Community empowerment has the meaning of giving strength / power to a group of people who are in a state of helplessness in order to become empowered and independent and have strength through synergistic processes and stages. The problem of community helplessness has been the main obstacle in the development of agrotourism villages, How Community Empowerment in the Development of Agrotourism Villages in Kuningan Regency is the focus of research to be carried out.

Community Empowerment Strategy in Agrotourism Development in Kuningan Regency can be carried out through various trainings, which are more initiated by tourism actors. While the government provides facilities in the form of providing places. One of the trainings that can be done is training to become a professional guide, training on homestay arrangement, and training on entrepreneurial spirit. If there are guests who come in large numbers, tourism actors can involve coral cadets, where the background of coral cadets has indeed been trained and has provisions in the field of tourism in accordance with tourism standards.

The community does not yet understand the concept of community-based agrotourism. The introduction of a community-based agrotourism model causes the community to know and agree to develop the business because it will have a wider impact on the village economy and job opportunities for the local community. Support from fruit products, processed products, the diversity of natural village panoramas and cultural potential has made the village community interested in developing it. This is realized by providing more in-depth information and input on plans and hopes to develop agrotourism. The development plan is outlined in the form of charts and maps about things that need to be worked on in the plan.

CONCLUSION

Kuningan Regency has agrotourism potential with superior objects, processed products made from plants and fruits, cultural uniqueness and beautiful panorama. The community really needs assistance both in the field of planning, development and management of agrotourism as well as assistance in the processing of post-harvest products. Agrotourism development needs to be carried out biophysical arrangement, social, cultural, institutional aspects, funding from the government and from other sources, marketing and increasing cooperation networks.

Recommendations for Agrotourism Development in Kuningan Regency include: Agrotourism potential and natural beauty synergized with the potential of processed products in the community can be offered to visitors, in agrotourism programs; Increasing human resource capacity in order to provide good service to visitor guests; Increased cooperation and stakeholder partnerships for agricultural sustainability and increased synergy between the agricultural sector and tourism.

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